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The mental-axiological aspect of L.E. Ulitskaya's prose of the 2010s is formed through the widest biblical-literary context, allusive, reminiscentative, interpretative and direct quotation of works of Russian classical literature of the XIX century, intertexts from the works of poets of the Silver Age and literature of the 60s - 80s of the XX century (up to I. Brodsky).

Russian Russian novels show not only the power of the Russian Word for a number of generations of Russian people, but also its crisis at the beginning of the XXI century under the influence of globalization processes [Ulitskaya 2011: 177], migration processes and the growth of atheistic sentiments among some of the youth. The indicator of the process of the revival of the "Russian word" in the work of L.E. Ulitskaya, the dynamics of the theme of righteousness, which is end-to-end for the writer's prose, presented in three forms, became an indicator of what is happening in the spiritual sphere of the personality of

THE AXIOLOGICAL CONTEXT OF THE EMBODIMENT OF THE THEME OF RIGHTEOUSNESS IN THE WORKS OF L.E. ULITSKAYA

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ABSTRACT

Comprehension of the ideological and artistic originality and aesthetic originality of the poetics of Ulitskaya's works, the study of the problem of the intertextuality of her work, first of all, using the example of new novels, should be considered scientifically substantiated and necessary. The analysis of intertextuality techniques in Ulitskaya's literary texts makes it possible to expand and deepen the understanding of the writer's artistic world and its evolution, to more clearly survey the ideological and aesthetic structure of the author's new works.

the beginning of the XXI century: actually, the traditional behavior of a devoutly believing person; moral righteousness and subconscious righteousness.

The creation of images of the righteous takes place at Ulitskaya using the gospel intertext, folklore mythologies and extensive literary citations from ancient Russian literature. A special symbolic mental sign in the novels is also the figurative-motivic system of the Silver Age, which through the intertext of literary works of this period demonstrates a departure from Orthodox values, loss of spiritual guidelines and fascination with the aesthetics of evil, which, in the end, according to the author, to a certain extent led to catastrophic consequences in Russia at the beginning of the XX century. A comparative analysis of the image of the poetry of the Silver Age created in the novels of L.E. Ulitskaya allows us to conclude that for L.E. Ulitskaya's novel "The Green Tent", the Silver Age is

important as a reflection of the post—Stalinism era, therefore, the author pays special attention to the work of banned poets - M. Tsvetaeva, A. Akhmatova, O. Mandelstam. The intertext of the poems of these poets is used to characterize the mental and spiritual state of the heroes of Ulitskaya, to express the author's position. In the novel "Jacob's Ladder", the identification of such an important feature of the mentality of the Russian people as literary centrality occurs in [Ulitskaya 2011: 177] mainly on the material of the works of A.P. Chekhov, poetry by Valery Bryusov (the image of Yakov Osetsky) and on the basis of images and motifs of classical world drama (the image of Nora). In all cases, we can say that literary centrality is one of the most important features of Lyudmila Ulitskaya's narrative manner.

The theme of righteousness runs through all the creativity of L.E. Ulitskaya. In her early stories and the novel "Medea and her Children", the idea is carried out that the sanctity of man lies, first of all, in family asceticism.

Researchers rightly attribute the maid Vasilisa to the characters of the hagiographic type of the novel "The Incident of Kukotsky", and in the novel "Daniel Stein, translator" — the main one the hero of the work. For example, D.M. Bychkov accurately noticed that Vasilisa belongs to a small number of church characters in the novel "The Incident of Kukotsky", although she is a minor, almost episodic character, and Daniel Stein is already becoming the central figure of the hagiographic narrative. "Observance of rituals of worship of God", worldly wisdom manifested in views on the surrounding world and on the relationships of people in

it, "secrecy and concealment" of suffering, rejection of self—centered self-interest and selfless sacrificial service to people - all these qualities speak about the Christian attitude of these characters [Bychkov 2011: 10].

According to D.M. Bychkov, Ulitskaya "accentuated" emphasizes the silence of the heroine and describes Vasilisa's appearance according to the iconographic canon, lengthens her figure, without correlating body parts and their normal proportions in the verbal portrait. The appearance of the foolish heroine is described by the author in accordance with her internal structure. Ulitskaya identifies Vasilisa's nature as an "inexhaustible source of gratitude", striving for goodness, forgetfulness and quick forgiveness of offenses [Ulitskaya 2006: 87].

The image of Vasilisa is realized in the novel not only through Evangelical intertexts, but also through the reception of "text within text": the author's attention to Vasilisa is embodied in the form of "life", i.e. literary.

The precedent phenomenon of the "Byzantine face" in the "Green Tent" is applied to the appearance of Antonina Naumovna. Although in this case, the "Byzantine face" that Antonina sees in herself testifies to the complete loss of the heroine's sober assessment of her actions. The images of the righteous at Ulitskaya are not always embodied through the characters of emphatically believing people. So, the righteous, in our opinion, is Anna Fedorovna from Ulitskaya's story "The Queen of Spades", who consciously and with meekness endured constant bullying from her nasty, depraved mother, bearing sacrifices, torment and humiliation right up to death. So, a believing daughter

sacrificed her beloved husband, children, and professional vocation for her mother and died for the sake of fulfilling her petty (culinary) desire.

The righteous were also the spouses from the story "And died in one day", which embodies the author's ideal of pure and faithful conjugal love. There is no doubt that Ulitskaya describes a person who lives according to the Truth of the Lord in a number of her other stories. So, in the cycle of stories "The People of our 145 Tsar", more than ten characters have already been described as righteous, whom the writer portrays with great sympathy and participation [Ulitskaya 2007].

The hagiographic tradition in Ulitskaya's prose is found in various forms. T.V. Sadovnikova is right when she writes that "in a series of ordinary daily affairs, the writer often discovers an "ordinary miracle", which allows you to connect some texts of L.E. Ulitskaya to the tradition of the Yuletide story" [Sadovnikova 2000: 89]. In addition to the story "Cabbage" from the cycle "Childhood-49", several stories from the cycle "People of our Tsar" can also be attributed to the Yuletide type of story, including "The Way of the Donkey", "Ladder Ladder", "The Great Teacher", telling about the Christmas miracle that came true by God's will.

All the works included in the book "People of our King" are devoted to the problem of finding God, who called the King of earthly and heavenly life. The story "The Way of the Donkey" is filled with Evangelical reminiscences, quotations and stories from the Sacred

The writings with which Ulitskaya creates images of the righteous main character and her guests. The main character lives in seclusion, as in a monastery, in a small

village, but her house is always full of friends who have become close people who love her and strive to communicate with her. To create the image of the righteous woman, Ulitskaya uses the symbolism of two life roads. One is an ancient Roman road created by pagans, the other, parallel to it, is a modern autobahn. Going to her old age (the second) way of vanity, the heroine changed it to the ancient loopy path of the donkey, which led her to the Truth: she began to live simply, endowing others with warmth and joy. It is no coincidence that a chapel with an icon of the Trinity stands at the crossroads, symbolizing the life cross of a person's destiny. The heroine lives simply, hospitably, away from the hustle and bustle and reconciled to what was before. Loneliness did not happen in the heroine's life, but she found spiritual harmony. The narrator varies the biblical plot and directly states this: "Christmas was happening — I didn't doubt it for a minute: strange, mixed, broken into separate pieces, but all the necessary elements were present: the baby, Mary and her old husband, the shepherd, the lamb was present, and the star gave a sign" [Ulitskaya 2007: 24].

In the text of Ulitskaya, a Christmas miracle happened: a sick boy spoke, everyone is happy. Although miracles are rejected by the narrator, because the baby did not recover completely, but the miracle happened. After all, the word "miracle" comes from the root "chuti" — to feel.

In the story "Corridor System", another righteous woman is presented — Zhenya's mother. The mother chose the path of faith, forgiveness, suffering, life with a man who needed to generously forgive his betrayal and his hatred for her. The mother heroine

was loved by others for her gentleness, mercy and forgiveness. Both her colleagues and her family came closer to faith with her: before her death, an icon of Sergius of Radonezh openly appears on the heroine's bedside table.

Therefore, the heroine of Ulitskaya leaves her life pacified, with gratitude to all those who hated and offended.

In the story "Short Circuit", the precedent phenomenon "heavenly light" becomes a symbol of life in God. Ivan Mstislavovich became blind in old age and began to live exclusively by the harmony of music. He feels that even in the darkness there is [Ulitskaya 2011: 143] a divine light that dissolves human tragedies, brightens the dirt of life, cleanses the souls of people. The hero thanks God that he is blind. It could have been worse. Now the harmony of life remains — this is the main thing, because God is felt in it. The hero gratefully chose

his path of righteousness, kindness and trust.

The book "People of our King" depicts various types of righteous people, but they are all united by faith and gratitude for everything that happened bad and good in their lives. In the story "The Great Teacher", the holy righteous grandmother of Gena caused the neglect of her grandson because of her senile infirmity.

Although Gena survived a miracle — he was saved by his grandmother's prayer during a terrible accident — he did not associate it with her holiness. Only after the death of the paralyzed grandmother, the grandson realized that she was a "great teacher of life", a secret nun, a spiritual sister of the great elder, that she had accomplished a real feat: after the closure of the monastery, she took in two orphans in the hungry years — his mother and aunt and raised them worthy people [Ulitskaya 2007: 52].

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